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Research Article

A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH ON PCI (PERCUTANEOUS CORONARY INTERVENTION, BLEEDING SITE & ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS IN CONTEXT TO MAJOR & MINOR BLEEDING & BLEEDING DEFINITIONS

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Abstract:

Objectives: This research aimed to find out the risk factors and bleeding association in the patients experiencing PCI (Percutaneous Coronary Intervention).

Methodology: We included 500 consecutive cases in our cross-sectional research who experienced PCI at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad (October, 2016 to December, 2017). We defined bleeding in per the criteria of "REPLACE – 2".

Results: Male to female proportion in our research was respectively 82 and 418 with respective percentage of 16.4% & 83.6% with a dominance of male over female. The factor of mean age was observed as (53.4 ± 9.6) years. Total complicated cases of bleeding were 31 (6.2%); further division was as that major and minor bleed cases were respectively 4 (0.8%) and 27 (5.6%). One death case was also reported because of (retroperitoneal) major bleeding. Female to male frequency of bleeding complication was respectively 8.5% & 5.7% with a significant P-value of (0.24). Majority of the cases were dealt with radial route (88.6%). Diabetic cases were involved in the risk because of the post-interventional bleeding (Odds Ratio as 6.4; P-value < 0.0001), hypertension (Odds Ratio: 13.2; P-value < 0.0001), smoking (Odds Ratio: 8.31; P-value < 0.0001) and BMI more than 40 (Odds Ratio: 6.8; P-value < 0.002), streptokinase use (Odds Ratio : 3.1; P-value < 0.0005), femoral approach (Odds Ratio : 4.2; P-value < 0.02), anemia (Odds Ratio : 44.8 ; P-value < 0.0001) and ACT ≥ 350 (Odds Ratio : 3.73 ; P-value < 0.0005). Procedure duration in females was (≥60) minutes with the use of IIIa inhibitors/ Glycoproteins IIb (GPI) in the above fifty years cases there was no relation of post-interventional bleeding.

Conclusion: There is a rare occurrence of the major bleeding related complications in the course of PCI which is one of the vital reason behind the mortality and morbidity proportions.

Key Words: Bleeding, Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI), Post-Operative, BMI and Site.

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INTRODUCTION:

Repeatedly observed non-cardiac complication is bleeding after PCI [1]. With the application of novel anti-platelets, anti-coagulants and glycoprotein IIb/IIIa inhibitors have reduced the incidence of ischemic complications but bleeding risk is still at large [2 – 4]. These complications result in the shape of increased hospital stay and cost, dissatisfaction of patient's mortality and morbidity [4 – 7].

There is a strong association of stroke, myocardial infarction and repeat procedures of revascularization after PCI [1, 8]. Bleeding may vary in the range of 1.4 – 12.8 percent after PCI [9, 10]. Adverse outcomes are associated with non-accessible bleeding sites [1, 7, 8, 11]. Blood transfusion is mandatory in five percent of the PCI patients which also increases mortality [10].

Older age, female gender, anemia, BMI, renal insufficiency, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, smoking etc. are among the contributing factors [1, 2, 6, 8, 12 – 14]. Other associated factors include ST-elevation myocardial infarction, emergency procedure, cardiogenic shock, femoral artery access, intervention duration, intra-aortic balloon pump use and larger sheath diameter [1, 2, 4, 10, 13, 15].

Bleeding episodes have been reduced from radial artery access, weight adjusted heparin vascular closure devices and direct thrombin inhibitor [3, 4, 5, 7, 15 – 18]. This research aimed to find out the risk factors and bleeding association in the patients experiencing PCI (Percutaneous Coronary Intervention).

METHODOLOGY:

We included 500 consecutive cases in our cross-sectional research who experienced PCI at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad (October, 2016 to December, 2017). We defined bleeding in per the criteria of "REPLACE – 2". The cases were of stable angina and ACS (Acute Coronary Syndromes). We did not include all the patients with previous diagnosis of bleeding diathesis and systemic bleeding, elevated creatinine and urea.

Major bleeding was referred to intraocular, intracranial, retroperitoneal or a clinical overt bleeding with hemoglobin drop (3 g/dl) or (4 g/dl) or two units blood transfusion (RBC). Clinical overt bleeding was not comparable with the mentioned criteria. Data of the patients was collected after informed consent. We documented bleeding site, bleeding events, hemodynamic status, hemoglobin level drop, blood transfusion frequency, outcomes and hospital stay duration.

Two hours prior to PCI every patient was managed with Aspirin (300 mg) and Clopidogrel (600 mg) with six french arterial sheath. Unfractionated heparin was given before intervention intravenous bolus (50 – 100 units/kg) to activate the clotting in the time period of (200 sec – 250 sec with GPI) and ACT of (300 sec – 350 sec without GPI).

Femoral or radial arterial access route, drug or bare metal eluting stent use and abciximab/epitifibatide/tirofiban GPI use was decided by the physician. The removal of arterial sheath was made after the procedure (ACT < 180 sec). A 24 hours monitoring was carried out, longer stay was prescribed in case of bleeding. Patients were discharged with an advice of reporting of any post procedure bleeding.

Data was analyzed on SPSS and presented in mean, percentage and \pm SD. Chi square was also applied for data comparison (P-value \leq 0.05).

RESULTS:

Male to female proportion in our research was respectively 82 and 418 with respective percentage of 16.4% & 83.6% with a dominance of male over female. The factor of mean age was observed as (53.4 \pm 9.6) years. Total complicated cases of bleeding were 31 (6.2%); further division was as that major and minor bleed cases were respectively 4 (0.8%) and 27 (5.6%). One death case was also reported because of (retroperitoneal) major bleeding. Female to male frequency of bleeding complication was respectively 8.5% & 5.7% with a significant P-value of (0.24). Outcomes about bleeding site and associated risk factors have been shown in Table I and II with respective figures.

Table – I: Sites of Bleeding

Type / Site	Number (31)	Percentage
Bruises (Arm, Shoulder, Back)	4	12.9
Epistaxis	1	3.2
G.I. Bleed	2	6.5
Gums	8	25.8
Hematoma (Arm)	7	22.6
Hematoma (Thigh)	7	22.6
Retroperitoneal	2	6.4

Table – II: Association of various Risk Factors with post-PCI bleeding

Risk Factor	Bleeders (31)	Non-Bleeders (469)	Odds Ratio	95% CI	Significance of Difference
Diabetes mellitus	74.20	30.90	6.4	2.8 – 14.7	P < 0.0001
Hypertension	87.10	33.70	13.2	4.5 – 38.5	P < 0.0001
Smoking	77.40	29.60	8.31	13.5 – 19.7	P < 0.0001
ACT ≥ 350	58.10	27.90	3.73	1.78 – 7.83	P < 0.0005
Female Gender	22.60	16.00	1.63	0.7 – 3.9	P = 0.28
BMI > 40	12.90	2.10	6.8	2.0 – 23.1	P < 0.002
Femoral Approach	17.20	4.90	4.2	1.9 – 9.4	P < 0.02
Use of SK within 24 hours preceding PCI	48.40	11.70	3.1	1.2 – 7.9	P < 0.0005
Anemia	58.50	3.10	44.8	19.9 – 100.9	P < 0.0001
Age ≥ 50 years	22.60	15.40	1.61	0.67 – 3.87	P = 0.25
Procedure Time (≥ 60 minutes)	12.90	8.13	2.17	0.71 – 6.6	P = 0.17
Use of Glycoprotein IIb/IIIa	93.50	89.30	0.95	0.57-1.61	P = 0.86

DISCUSSION:

Outcomes about rare major bleeding and post-PCI bleeding were observed as 0.8% and 6.2%. Various patients and therapies had various bleeding proportions with a bleeding reduction trend [2, 3, 5, 12, 17, 19]. REPLACE – 2 trials had less bleeding in the perspective of novel PCI [3, 12]. Two authors reported major bleeding in the trials of “STEEPLE” as 6.5% & 5.4% [6, 11]. TIMI trial was used by Kinnard while major and minor bleeding was 5.4% and 12.7% [10]. Universal definition of bleeding requires a consensus as numerous trials are under consideration and six grades were introduced from grade Zero – Six that is no bleeding to severe bleeding [9, 19]. We observed less incidence of bleeding in comparison to the previously observed

research studies, radial route was observed in abundance in (88.6%). Radial route is preferred because of reduced complications, patients’ preference, early ambulation and convenience. RIVAL (radial versus femoral) access trial also reduced bleeding (64%) with a complication rate of 1.4% in the vascular site [17]. Radial access is less common in USA [20].

Our mean age can be compared with previous research population trend (53.4 ± 9.6) years [21]. Higher bleeding was observed in West because of frequent employment of high risk cases and transfemoral route. Bleeding site and risk factors can also be compared with the previous local research studies as shown in both the tables [16, 22].

Obese and overweight cases were included in our population of PCI as mean BMI was (28.7 ± 5.1) with frequent vascular access hematomas (high in females, 57.14%), which is also comparable with other research outcomes [12, 18].

Development of femoral access was observed in two cases and one female sixty-year-old patient died (diabetic, hypertensive, BMI = 28.9 and additional groin hematoma with retroperitoneal hematoma, seventy minutes interventional duration, double bolus infusion and eptifibatide, ACT = 290) expired in the twenty-four hours.

According to the report of BMC-2 association of bivalirudin was observed with low risk factors [15]. Major gastrointestinal bleeding was observed in 2 cases (0.4%, both genders > 65 Years), patients showed a history of hypertension, baseline anemia and diabetes. There are also reports of gastrointestinal bleeding as (21% & 3.5%) in previous studies with diabetes, older age, baseline anemia and smoking as markers [8, 11, 13].

Higher bleeding was associated with diabetes, smoking, hypertension and baseline anemia [2, 4, 6, 8, 13]. Higher bleeding was also linked with the anemic patients and ACT (≥ 350 seconds). Brenner observed a linear increase in bleeding risk as ACT (365 seconds) (P-value = 0.01) [14]. Independent association of elevated unfractionated heparin weight was observed with increased bleeding [14].

Significant association was found between bleeding events and 24-hours of thrombolysis with streptokinase PCI. According to NORDISTEMI research twelve hourly (thrombolysis) GUSTO severe bleeding was observed in (1.9%) cases [23]. Literature has also revealed association of bleeding with advanced age, prolonged interventional duration, Glycoprotein IIb/IIIa (GPI) use and female gender [1 – 4, 6, 10, 12, 15].

Blood transfusion was made in 4 cases (0.8%); whereas, Kinnard reported (5.4%) cases. Blood transfusion dead cases were (10.6%, major bleeding) in comparison to the (5.1%, major bleeding without blood transfusion) with one unit one-year mortality rate [10].

CONCLUSION:

There is a rare occurrence of the major bleeding related complications in the course of PCI which is one of the vital reason behind the mortality and morbidity proportions.

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